

PEDAGOGICAL SCIENCES

THE MAIN ASPECTS OF A TEACHER'S PROFESSIONAL COMPETENCE

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Abstract

The article is devoted to the study of the professional competence of a teacher, which is considered as a set of knowledge, skills and personal qualities necessary for the successful implementation of educational activities. The authors analyze the key components of competence, including psychological, conflict, informational, and communicative components. Special attention is paid to continuous learning skills, readiness for innovation and adaptation in the information society. The importance of personality-oriented and individually creative approaches in educational practice is also emphasized. The article emphasizes the importance of competence for the formation of a competitive teacher who is able to work effectively in the face of modern challenges and ensure the high quality of the educational process.

Keywords: competence, professional activity, effective teacher, concentration, professional skill.

For a long time, researchers have been paying considerable attention to the study of the qualities necessary for teachers for professional activity. In the course of these studies, the content of professional competence was determined, as well as pedagogical, psychological and social factors contributing to its development were identified. Despite the variety of terms and approaches, the authors agree that professional competence includes three main elements: theoretical, practical and personal levels.

According to I.D. Lapteva, professional competence can be divided into key, basic and special. The key competence helps a person to successfully adapt to the dynamic conditions of the modern world, the basic one describes the specifics of a particular field of knowledge, and the special one focuses on specific professional skills.

The teaching profession combines transformative and managerial functions, and in order to effectively manage the student development process, the teacher must be highly qualified. The concept of professional competence of a teacher reflects his theoretical and practical readiness to perform the tasks of educational activity, which is the basis of his professionalism. Researchers identify more than 30 types of competencies and use the term "pedagogical competence" along with the term "professional competence" (V.A.Slastenin, I.F.Isaev, A.I.Mishchenko, E.N.Shiyanov, V.N.Vvedensky, etc.) (L.M.Mitina, V.A.Andreeva, T.G.Argunova, etc.).

The term "competence" comes from the Latin word *competentio*, which means "to conform" or "to achieve". In the modern context, competence is defined as the ability of a professional to cope with a certain

range of tasks. "The reform of the education system assumes that the main result of the educational institution's activities should be a set of competencies, the mastery of which allows solving problems in everyday, professional and social life. This approach, adopted by the majority of highly developed countries, where there has been a reorientation towards mastering key competencies in intellectual, civil law, communication, information and other fields, is fully consistent with the traditional values of domestic education, where the main purpose of education is to focus on understanding the scientific world, spirituality, and social activity" [1]. This concept also covers the formal requirements for the personal and professional qualities of specialists.

N. V. Kharitonova [2], based on the complex of skills developed by a specialist, identifies: design competence – skills necessary to determine tactical and strategic tasks through which the professional process is realized; information and predictive competence – constructive skills of compositional ordering of knowledge; organizational competence – skills of managing activities; communicative competence – communication skills impact on the subjects of the professional process; analytical competence is the ability to adequately assess the level of one's own activities.

K. Angelowski suggests considering the professional competence of a teacher through the prism of pedagogical skills, which he divides into four main groups:

1. The ability to transform general educational goals into specific pedagogical tasks. This includes studying students and teams in order to identify their

readiness for learning, as well as designing their further development.

2. The ability to create and structure a pedagogical system, including task planning, selection of methods and forms of organization.

3. The skill of identifying the links between various aspects of the educational process and their implementation.

4. The ability to analyze and evaluate the results of educational activities, as well as formulate new tasks for further work.[3]

One of the key qualities that characterize professional competence is initiative. This quality is expressed in the desire for innovative forms of work and the ability to take responsibility. In addition, an important element of professional competence is cooperation based on a humanistic approach and the joint work of the teacher and students.

The key skill of teachers is the ability to analyze and relate various elements and factors of the educational process. This includes creating the necessary conditions, such as a material base, moral and psychological support, and organizational resources. An important aspect is to stimulate the activity of students, their personal growth and the development of their independent activities. This approach makes it possible to achieve a harmonious combination of all components of the educational process, creating the basis for successful education.

An effective teacher should be able not only to conduct self-analysis of his work, but also to objectively evaluate the educational process and the results achieved. Such an analysis helps to identify the strengths and weaknesses of pedagogical practice, identify the main priorities and identify tasks that require priority solutions. This allows the teacher to improve his activities, adapt them to changing conditions and achieve the best results. Initiative is also one of the most important indicators of a teacher's professional competence. This quality is expressed in the desire for innovation, the ability to propose and implement new forms of work. Initiative can be considered as a kind of social activity and creative potential. It manifests itself when a teacher takes on increased responsibility, going beyond the standard expectations and social norms. Another important element of competence is the ability to work in collaboration with others. This is a humanistic concept based on the joint activities of children and adults, which involves mutual understanding, deep insight into each other's spiritual world, as well as a collective analysis of the process and its results. Cooperation contributes to building trust, creating a favorable educational environment and effective interaction between all participants in the process.

A review of scientific sources shows that the problem of professional competence of a teacher is considered from different points of view. Some authors use the term "professional competence", others — "pedagogical competence". In some works, these concepts are combined within the framework of professional and pedagogical activity, which leads to the emergence of the term "professional and pedagogical competence".

Pedagogical competence is a systemic phenomenon that combines the knowledge, experience, skills and personal qualities of a teacher. These components ensure the successful fulfillment of professional tasks aimed at organizing the educational process and interacting with students. In addition, pedagogical competence presupposes continuous personal development and professional improvement.

The personality of the teacher plays a dominant role in the structure of professional competence. Its main components include:

Personal motivation, characterized as the direction of the interests and priorities of the teacher, which determine his approach to work.

Personality traits, which include pedagogical abilities, character, emotional and psychological characteristics.

Integral characteristics that include pedagogical self-awareness, individual work style, creativity and creativity.

These characteristics determine the teacher's ability to effectively perform his professional duties, creating conditions for the development of both his students and himself.

For the formation of a teacher's professional competence, basic psychological and pedagogical knowledge is needed, as well as knowledge of the subject, but their presence in itself is not a sufficient condition. This knowledge creates the basis for the development of intellectual and practical skills, which then turn into skills.

Theoretical, practical and methodological training act as a catalyst for the formation of future teachers' ability to solve problems related to education and upbringing. However, this knowledge is only a prerequisite for achieving a higher level of professionalism.

Pedagogical skills are a sequence of actions aimed at fulfilling professional tasks. These actions are often based on theoretical knowledge and may include elements brought to automatism. The main goal of pedagogical skills is to promote the harmonious development of students' personality. This understanding underlines the importance of theoretical knowledge as the basis for the formation of practical readiness of teachers. The unity of theoretical and practical training allows future teachers to develop pedagogical skills at various levels — from basic reproductive to more complex creative. Automating individual actions makes it possible to increase work efficiency.

One of the most important elements characterizing the professional competence of a teacher is initiative. This quality is manifested in the desire to create and implement new approaches to educational activities. Initiative is associated with an intrinsic motivation to find innovative solutions and take responsibility for their implementation. In practice, this means that the teacher takes on tasks that go beyond the standard requirements, demonstrating a high level of social activity and creative potential. This quality helps him not only to fulfill his duties, but also to become a leader in the educational environment. Cooperation is another important aspect of professional competence. It is based on the principles of joint activity between the

teacher and the students, which are based on mutual understanding, trust and a collective analysis of learning processes and outcomes. Cooperation helps to strengthen a positive atmosphere in the learning environment, which, in turn, increases the effectiveness of the educational process. It also allows students to take into account their individual characteristics, creating conditions for their personal and intellectual growth. Competence can be defined as the degree to which a specialist's knowledge, skills, and experience meet the requirements and challenges they face in their professional activities. This concept covers both personal and professional aspects, including the ability to adapt to difficult conditions and solve non-standard problems.

Modern research identifies several key types of competence that are necessary for a teacher:

1. Special competence is the ability to perform professional activities at a high level and the ability to project their professional growth.
2. Social competence — includes skills of interaction in a group, the ability to cooperate and take responsibility for the results of professional activity.
3. Personal competence is associated with the ability to express and develop oneself, as well as to resist professional deformations.
4. Individual competence — reflects the ability to self-actualize, develop one's uniqueness within the profession and the ability to maintain professional stability. "The professional competence of a teacher of a particular specialty is a normative model, reflecting the scientifically based composition of professional knowledge, skills, methods of activity and expresses the unity of his theoretical and practical readiness in the integral structure of personality" [4]. Recent research highlights the importance of political and social competencies for educators. These skills include the ability to participate in collective decision-making and to support and develop democratic institutions. In the context of globalization, teachers need to be able to work in a multinational and multicultural environment. This requires not only understanding and respect for differences, but also the ability to interact effectively with people of different cultures, languages, and religions.

Teacher competence is a multifaceted phenomenon that combines a wide range of knowledge, skills, and personal qualities. Its development requires constant improvement, including both theoretical and practical training. A successful teacher is someone who is able not only to adapt to changes, but also to actively shape the future of the educational environment.

One of the key competencies required by a modern specialist is the mastery of oral and written communication skills. These skills not only facilitate interaction in a professional environment, but also play a crucial role in social adaptation. Persons deprived of such skills may face isolation in society. Knowledge of several languages is of particular importance in this category, which is becoming increasingly relevant in the context of globalization. In modern conditions, when information technology plays a key role, competencies in this area are becoming necessary. This includes the ability to use new technologies, understand their ad-

vantages and limitations, and critically analyze information coming through the media and the Internet. Such skills allow you to work effectively with large amounts of data and avoid manipulation by information sources.

Another important category of competencies is related to readiness for continuous learning. These skills involve striving for self-development in both professional and personal life. The ability to learn throughout life is an important prerequisite for successful adaptation to the rapidly changing conditions of the modern world.

Modern research identifies several key types of competencies that ensure professional success.:

1. Educational and cognitive competence. This category includes planning, analysis, and reflection skills. Specialists with this competence are able to effectively solve non-standard tasks using creative approaches and statistical methods.

2. Information competence. It is the ability to work with information technologies for searching, analyzing, processing and transmitting data.

3. Communication competence. It involves the ability to interact with others, work in a team, and take on various social roles.

These approaches help teachers to master not only basic professional skills, but also to develop unique personal qualities necessary for successful work.

In the context of rapid changes in society and the increasing complexity of professional tasks, teaching requires a high degree of competence, which is becoming a key factor in the successful fulfillment of professional duties. The teacher's competencies, which include a wide range of knowledge, skills and personal qualities, are the basis of a high-quality educational process focused on the formation of a successful student's personality.

Psychological and conflict competencies play a special role in the professional activity of a teacher. Knowledge of the age and individual characteristics of students, the ability to build an educational process tailored to their needs, as well as the ability to manage conflict situations make a teacher successful not only in professional but also in personal communication. These competencies make it possible to create a favorable educational environment conducive to unlocking the potential of each student. Individualization of learning is also becoming an important element of modern pedagogy. Personality-oriented and creative approaches allow teachers to adapt the educational process to the unique needs of students, contributing to their personal and intellectual development. Flexibility in the choice of teaching methods and forms helps the teacher to remain relevant and effective in the context of a variety of educational tasks.

The modern education system requires teachers not only to be professional, but also to be ready for constant change. Competence becomes the most important criterion of a teacher's competitiveness, allowing him to be in demand in the labor market and inspire students and colleagues by his example.

Thus, the professional competence of a teacher is a complex and multifaceted phenomenon that combines

a wide range of knowledge, skills and personal qualities. It requires constant improvement, striving for self-development and openness to innovation. Only through the conscious development of their competence can a teacher become not just a teacher, but a mentor who forms in his students not only the knowledge, but also the life values necessary for their successful adaptation in a rapidly changing world.

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